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Geomorphic Distribution Modeling of Desert Pavements: Towards a Global Assessment

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1

Abstract— Desert pavements, characterized by a stone layer over fine eolian materials, are key geomorphological features in arid regions and play a critical role in the global dust cycle. Despite their importance, quantitative evidence regarding their global distribution remains limited. This study provides a preliminary assessment of desert pavement distribution using a GIS-based multiple-criteria decision analysis (GIS-MCDA) framework. Key environmental factors, including climate, topography, vegetation, soil texture, and anthropogenic disturbance, were incorporated into a global favorability index at a 1 km × 1 km resolution. Validation against 20 documented desert-pavement research sites revealed a significant association with high index values, with 15% of sites exhibiting an index ≥ 0.90 and 80% ≥ 0.75 . The model estimates that up to 25.7 million km², or 19.0% of the Earth's land surface, holds potential for desert pavements. These results provide a foundation for future studies, emphasizing the need for localized, high-resolution research and the integration of geomorphometric and remote-sensing techniques with machine-learning models. This initial global assessment underscores the utility of GIS-MCDA in geomorphic distribution modeling and highlights the importance of refining global environmental datasets for arid landscapes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Desert pavements are widespread yet complex geomorphological phenomena in desert environments worldwide and are key components of the global dust cycle [1, 2, 3]. Characterized by a distinct stone layer above fine, eolian materials, their distribution is constrained by a combination of topographic, hydroclimatic, geomorphic, and biological processes. Despite their prevalence and geomorphic importance, knowledge regarding their distribution, characteristics, and environmental feedback mechanisms within the Earth system remains limited. Surprisingly, despite global mapping efforts for many other land surface characteristics, quantitative evidence of their distribution and significance is still scarce, though anecdotal estimates suggest that nearly 50% of arid land surfaces feature desert pavements (defining 'arid' as mean annual precipitation < 250 mm) [4].

This study aims to provide an initial assessment of the potential global distribution of desert pavements. Confronted with methodological challenges, particularly the scarcity of suitable training data for supervised classification modeling using machine-learning or statistical techniques, this study adopts a pragmatic approach. By utilizing prescriptive cartographic models

TABLE I. CRITERIA AND DATA SOURCES USED FOR THE GIS-BASED MULTICRITERIA ANALYSIS OF POTENTIAL DESERT PAVEMENT DISTRIBUTION.

Theme	Variable and source	Suitable range	Locally suitable
Ecoregion	Köppen–Geiger ecoregions 1991-2020 [8]	BWh, BWk	BSh, BSk
Climate	CHELSA V2.1 precipitation data 1981-2010 [9, 10]	70-200 mm	<70 mm, 200-320 mm
Vegetation	Barren land in Global 1-km Consensus Land Cover [11]	>90%	80-90%
Topography	Slope angle, Standard deviation of elevation from Global 1 km land surface parameters dataset [12]	<2° <25 m	2-5° 25-40 m
Soil texture	Ratio of coarse fraction in top to underlying layer; SoilGrids 250 m [13]	Ratio >0.95	n/a
Anthropogenic disturbance	Nighttime lit surface fraction [14]	<5%	5-10%
Water bodies	Percent water body from Global 1 km land surface parameters dataset [12]	0%	<20%

within a GIS-based multiple-criteria decision analysis (GIS-MCDA) framework [5], the research integrates geomorphological expertise with available global GIS datasets. This approach, while preliminary, leverages local evidence from existing publications for validation, offering a foundation for more rigorous future studies using supervised statistical and machine-learning models that have been successful in other geomorphic distribution modeling tasks [6, 7].

II. METHODS AND DATA

To explore the geographic distribution of desert pavements, the proposed GIS-MCDA approach leverages global GIS datasets representing first-order limiting factors of desert pavement distribution. The model does not aim to pinpoint exact locations but instead delineates an “envelope” of their potential distribution.

Specifically, the thematic aspects considered are climate [8], topography [9], vegetation [10], soil texture [11], and anthropogenic disturbance [12] (Table 1), sourced at or downscaled to a ~1 km resolution. Each GIS layer is reclassified into “suitable,” “locally suitable,” and “unsuitable,” with ratings of 1.0, 0.5, and 0 assigned, respectively. These ratings layers are combined into a weighted average to create a global favorability index. The climate and the vegetation layer are double weighted.

The chosen criteria reflect general characteristics of environments that are favorable for the presence of desert pavements, while accounting for the fact that the chosen global GIS layers are strongly generalized and therefore exhibit significant variation in environmental conditions within a grid cell. Moreover, the climatic and soil texture input layers are themselves model outputs that are based on sparse observational data from desert environments, affecting their accuracy, and ultimately all GIS layers are only proxies for possible processes that favor or

inhibit the existence of desert pavements. Against this background, the “suitable” and “locally suitable” categories were defined, generally following the distributional statistics of these variables for 20 desert pavement research sites identified in the literature.

Since rainfall events, and even rare high-intensity events, may erode or bury a superficial stone layer, only Köppen–Geiger desert climates were identified as being fully suitable, while steppe ecoregions may be locally suitable [8], and a global precipitation climatology was accessed to obtain quantitative evidence [9, 10]. Desert pavement evidences are also concentrated in barren land based on a consensus vegetation density dataset [11]; it serves as an important exclusion criterion since root-forming plants stabilize the soil and are associated with increased bioturbation. Indirectly, vegetation may also indicate more humid conditions.

Topography controls not only erosion and deposition by wind and water, but also the availability and downslope displacement of clasts forming the surface layer. A coarse-resolution slope angle criterion and the within-cell elevation standard deviation [12] are both informative indicators based on the available evidence. The geomorphometric data from the Global 1-km land surface parameters dataset [12] is based on the Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain DEM (MERIT DEM, 90 m resolution) [13].

By definition, a seemingly ideal indicator of desert pavement is the ratio of coarse material in the top layer versus the underlying layers in globally available gridded soil data products [14]. Nevertheless, the machine-learning models used to generate SoilGrids data must extrapolate empirical rules from more densely sampled, often more humid regions into the extremely data-poor desert environments relevant to this study (e.g., Namibia: 1.7 soil profiles per 1000 km²). Because of this, it was decided to give this layer (only) an equal weight, balancing the high relevance of this layer against its large uncertainties. Finally, anthropogenic

Figure 1. Potential global distribution range of desert pavements based on GIS-MCDA. Larger index values indicate a higher favorability for desert pavements. Field sites with coordinates identifiable in the literature are marked with red crosses (from West to East: Mojave Desert, California; Black Rock Desert, Utah; Atacama, Chile; Patagonia, Argentina; Fuerteventura, Spain; Negev, Israel; Badia Desert, Jordan; Gobi, Mongolia; Strzelecki Desert, Australia).

disturbance, as represented by a location's nighttime lit surface fraction [15], helps to identify and exclude areas in which soils are more likely disturbed due to urban sprawl or along major infrastructure or mine sites.

A preliminary validation of the model's predictive capacity was conducted by comparing its outputs against the locations of 20 documented desert pavement field sites across diverse arid regions.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The empirical validation showed that 15% of the desert pavement field sites exhibited a favorability index value ≥ 0.90 , while 80% had an index value greater than ≥ 0.75 . These areas should be prioritized for further refinement using higher-resolution environmental data and supervised classification techniques.

The GIS-MCDA yielded significant insights into the potential global distribution of desert pavements, as shown in Figure 1. According to the derived index, an estimated 12.1 million km², or approximately 9.0% of the Earth's total land surface (excluding Antarctica), has a high favorability index value (≥ 0.90), indicating that the favorability criteria are nearly fully satisfied. This high-favorability area corresponds to 50.0% of all arid land (<250 mm). Relaxing the threshold to include areas with an index value ≥ 0.75 expands the potential area to 25.7 million km², or 19.0% of the

Earth's land surface. It covers 88.7% of all arid land and partly extends beyond it.

Considering the case of Namibia (Figure 2), where our future research will be focused, it becomes evident that some areas with high favorability index values may exhibit a high dust emission potential, making desert pavements as accretionary features less likely. This is especially true for coastal areas in Namibia.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

Our GIS-based multicriteria analysis demonstrates promise in delineating an initial global distribution of desert pavements using globally available environmental datasets. Despite encouraging validation results using sparse evidence from the literature, this research exposes critical gaps in the specificity and thematic depth of current global soil datasets for arid environments.

This study serves as an exploratory step, suggesting that future efforts should prioritize localized, high-resolution studies to generate refined data that better capture the relationships between local topography and desert pavement formation and preservation. An additional variable that should be incorporated in future model enhancements is modeled atmospheric dust flux [16]. Remote sensing data could further complement this approach, aiding in the differentiation of stable, stone-covered surfaces from other desert soils [17].

Figure 2. Potential desert pavement distribution in Namibia based on GIS-MCDA.

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